

Supplementary materials 2 (s.m.2)

The first report on detecting SARS-CoV-2 inside bacteria of the human gut microbiome: A case series on asymptomatic family members and a child with COVID-19

[version 2; peer review: 2 approved with reservations, 1 not approved]

<https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.77421.2>

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Additional note to integrate the supplementary materials published at
<https://zenodo.org/badge/DOI/10.5281/zenodo.6974414.svg>

1. Stool samples are processed within 24 hours of collection to minimize changes in microbial composition.
2. The authors used water for simplicity and to avoid introducing molecular complexity that could interfere with the discovery phase.
3. An equal volume of washing solution (50 mM NaHCO₃ in this case) is used to wash the homogenized stool sample.
4. Washing with 50 mM NaHCO₃ has been done to remove debris and impurities from the stool sample and to adjust the pH of the sample, promoting the growth of specific bacterial populations.
5. Resuspending of the pellet in 10 mM NaCl has been done to create a more suitable osmotic environment for bacterial growth.
6. 0.1 mL of resuspended sample was added to 10 mL of nutrient broth in a 50 mL conical flask or a similar-sized tube.
7. The authors also focused on specific facultative aerobic or anaerobic bacteria present in the gut microbiome to also test their activity, although the use of semi-anaerobic conditions would have provided a more accurate representation of the gut environment.
8. The supplementary materials are only a brief and outline description. Culture was conducted up to 30 days, and in the supplementary materials, only directions for the first 7 days were given, so in the same method cultures can be conducted beyond 7 days.
9. The arbitrary units result from a normalization coefficient that eliminates the dimension and stabilizes signal oscillation. In the analytical field, this approach is considered fundamental for obtaining cleaner and more comparable signals [1]. Absolute units can be highly unstable, and their use for quantitation is rare. In fact, arbitrary units are also employed with Luminex technology, especially in multiresidues analysis [2]. Regarding the limit of detection for the assay, we have set it at 3 amu, considering the noise level is normalized to 1 cut-off.

Correction of unit in table 1sm

The value of table 1S are reported in Arbitrary Unit or median fluorescence intensity (MFI) obtained after noise subtraction.

Table 1s

<i>Absolute value Arbitrary Units (AU) or Median fluorescence intensity (MFI)</i>	<i>Stools Luminex AU Test before therapy (Initial)</i>	<i>Absolute value</i>	<i>Stools L u m i n e x A U Test 60 days after therapy (Final)</i>
<i>10.0+/-0.1</i>	<i>24</i>	<i>7.1+/-0.1</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>9.9+/-0.1</i>	<i>23</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>11.2+/-0.1</i>	<i>33</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>9.5+/-0.1</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>9.5+/-0.1</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>6.6+/-0.1</i>	<i>13</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>9.1+/-0.1</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>6.4+/-0.1</i>	<i>12</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>9.5+/-0.1</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>0</i>	<i>0</i>
<i>10.0+/-0.1</i>	<i>24</i>	<i>220+/-2.0</i>	<i>520</i>

References:

1. Lehman GJ, McGill SM. The importance of normalization in the interpretation of surface electromyography: a proof of principle. *J Manipulative Physiol Ther.* 1999 Sep;22(7):444-6. doi: 10.1016/s0161-4754(99)70032-1.
2. Bandiera S, Lebas A, Canizares-Martinello L, Guinchard F, Lyonnais C, Perrin S, Nicolas M, Uhlich S, Chabaud-Riou M. A single immunogenicity assay for testing potency of combination DTaP

vaccines: Simultaneous quantitation of anti-DT, anti-TT, anti-PTxd and anti-FHA antibodies in Guinea-pig serum with a Luminex®-xMAP® bead-based serological assay. *Biologicals*. 2019 Sep;61:15-21. doi: 10.1016/j.biologicals.2019.08.002. Epub 2019 Aug 23.